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SURUNKALI POLIPOZ RINOSINUSITLARNI DAVOSINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH

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ANNOTATSIYA

Polipoz rinosinusit (PRS) — burun bo'shlig'i shilliq qavatining surunkali yallig'lanish kasalligi. Shubhasiz, PRS zamonaviy tibbiyotda jadal va hal etilmagan muammodir. Poliklinikalardagi LOR-kabinetlarga murojaat qilayotgan orasida 5 foizni, allergologga murojaat qiluvchilar orasida 4 foizni tashkil etadi.

Surunkali polipli rinosinusit bilan og'rig'an 161 bemorda kompleks davolash qo'llanildi.

Birinchi guruhda (29 bemor) jarrohlik simptomatik davolash bilan, ikkinchi guruhda (92 bemor) jarrohlik davolash antigistaminik preparatlarni og'iz orqali qabul qilish va burun shilliq qavatiga gioksison malhamini surtish bilan birlashtirildi.

Uchinchi guruhdagi bemorlar (40 kishi) ikkinchisiga o'xshash tarzda davolandilar, ammo ularda natriy tiosulfatning tomir ichiga yuborishlari ham qo'llanildi.

Darhol va uzoq muddatli natijalar 3d guruhidagi bemorlarda yaxshiroq bo'lib chiqdi.

Kalit so'zlar. Polipli rinosinusit (PRS), konservativ davolash, jarrohlik amaliyoti.

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OPTIMIZING THE TREATMENT OF CHRONIC POLYPOSIS RHINOSINUSITIS

ABSTRACT

Polypous rhinosinusitis (PRS) is a chronic inflammatory disease of the mucous membrane of the nasal cavity and paranasal sinuses, characterized by the formation and recurrent growth of polyps, consisting predominantly of edematous tissue infiltrated with eosinophils. Undoubtedly, PRS

represents a very serious and unresolved problem in modern medicine. Patients with PRS make up 5% of those visiting ENT clinics and 4% of those visiting an allergist.

Complex treatment was used in 161 patients with chronic polypous rhinosinusitis.

In the first group (29 patients) surgery was combined with a symptomatic treatment, in the second group (92 patients) surgical treatment was combined with peroral intake of antihistaminic drugs and application of hyoxyson ointment to the nasal mucosa.

Patients of the third group (40 persons) were treated in a way similar to that of the second one, but intravenous injections of sodium thiosulfate was also used in them.

Immediate and long-term results appeared to be better in patients of the 3d group.

Keywords. Polypous rhinosinusitis (PRS), symptomatic treatment , surgical treatment.

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ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ХРОНИЧЕСКОГО ПОЛИПОЗНОГО РИНОСИНУСИТА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Полипозный риносинусит (ПРС) - хроническое воспалительное заболевание слизистой оболочки полости носа и околоносовых пазух, характеризующееся образованием и рецидивирующим ростом полипов, состоящих преимущественно из отечной ткани, инфильтрированной эозинофилами. Бесспорно, ПРС представляет собой очень серьезную и нерешенную проблему в современной медицине. Пациенты с ПРС составляют 5% среди обращающихся в ЛОР-кабинеты поликлиник и 4% среди обращающихся к аллергологу).

Комплексное лечение применено у 161 больного хроническим полипозным риносинуситом.

В первой группе (29 больных) оперативное вмешательство сочеталось с симптоматическим лечением, во второй группе (92 больных) хирургическое лечение сочеталось с пероральным приемом антигистаминных препаратов и аппликацией мази Гиоксисон на слизистую оболочку носа.

Больных третьей группы (40 человек) лечили аналогично второй группе, но им также применяли внутривенные инъекции тиосульфата натрия.

Непосредственные и отдаленные результаты оказались лучше у пациентов 3-й группы.

Ключевые слова. Полипозные риносинуситы (ПРС), консервативная терапия, хирургическое лечение.

So‘nggi paytlarda eksudativ sinusit bilan kasallangan bemorlarni davolashda muayyan muvaffaqiyatlarga erishildi. L. B. Daynyak ma'lumotiga ko‘ra, dori-darmonlar bilan davolash usulining qo‘llanilishi burun yon bo‘shliqlarida o‘tkaziladigan jarrohlik aralashuvlari sonini 70%ga qisqartirdi. Ammo ushbu holat konservativ davo usullarining samarasi past bo‘lgan qaytalanuvchi polipoz rinosinuitga unchalik ham to‘g‘ri kelmaydi, chunki ular polipozning qaytalanishini oldini olmaydi (5,6,7).

Ko‘pgina klinitstlarning kuzatuvlari va bizning shaxsiy tadqiqotlarimiz polipoz rinosinuit qaytalanishga moyil ekanligini ko‘rsatadi. Poliplar to‘liq olib tashlanganidan keyin ham bir necha oydan keyin burundan nafas olishning qiyinlashuvi ro‘y beradi va bemorlar takroriy operatsiyalar uchun kasalxonaga yotqiziladi.(1,2,3)

V. Korsakov, V. T. Palchun burun va burun yon bo‘shliqlari polipozini allergik ko‘rinish deb hisoblashadi. Shuning uchun ushbu patologiyada bemorlarni davolash keng qamrovli bo‘lishi, ya‘ni jarrohlik yo‘li orqali davolashni dori-darmonlar - organizmning desensibilizatsiyasi bilan birlashtirish lozim.

Surunkali polipoz rinosinuit bilan kasallangan bemorlarni davolash haqidagi adabiyot ma'lumotlarini to'rt guruhga birlashtirish mumkin.

1. Burun yon bo'shliqlarida o'tkaziladigan operativ aralashuvlarni organizmning mikroba antigeniga qarshi desensibilizatsiyasi bilan parallel ravishda amalga oshiriladi.
2. Operatsiyalar organizmning to'qimali polip antigeniga qarshi desensibilizatsiyasi bilan birga o'tkaziladi.
3. Burun yon bo'shliqlarida o'tkaziladigan operativ aralashuvlarni va organizmning desensibilizatsiyasini kortikosteroidli va antigistamin preparatlar bilan amalga oshiriladi.
4. Burun yon bo'shliqlarida o'tkaziladigan operativ aralashuvlarni Vidiyev nervini kesish va nerv cho'ltog'ining markaziy qismini koagulyatsiya qilish bilan birga o'tkaziladi.

Keltirilgan ma'lumotlar ko'plab davolash muassasalarida qo'llanilishi bilan qanoatlanadigan faqat bitta operativ davolash usuli yetarlicha samarali emasligini ko'rsatadi, chunki polipozning qaytalanishi bir necha oydan keyin yana sodir bo'ladi.

Tadqiqotning maqsadi surunkali polipozli rinosinuit bilan og'riq bemorlarni davolashni optimallashtirishdan iborat.

Materiallar va tadqiqot usullari: 2017-2023 yillarda surunkali polipoz rinosinuit bilan kasallangan 164 nafar bemor bizning kuzatuvimiz ostida edi. Erkaklar 102 nafar, ayollar 62 nafardan iborat edi. 15 yoshdan 20 yoshgacha - 6 nafar, 21 yoshdan 30 yoshgacha— 24 nafar, 31 yoshdan 40 yoshgacha — 36 nafar, 41 yoshdan 50 yoshgacha— 51 nafar, 51 yoshdan 60 yoshgacha— 31 nafar va 60 yoshdan oshganlar— 16 nafar bemor bo'lgan. Kasallik davomiyligi bo'yicha – kasallik 62 nafar bemorda 3 yilgacha, 35 nafar bemorda 5 yilgacha, 38 nafar bemorda 10 yilgacha, 17 nafar bemorda 15 yilgacha, 9 nafar bemorda 20 yilgacha va 3 nafar bemorda 20 yildan ortiq davom etgan. Ikki tomonlama surunkali polipoz rinosinuit 99 nafar, bir tomonlama patologiya— 37 nafar, ikki tomonlama polipoz etmoidit 22 nafar, bir tomonlama jarayon 6 nafar bemorda tashxisot etilgan. Anamnestik ma'lumotlardan aniqlanishicha, 164 nafar bemordan 57 nafarida polipotomiya, 35 nafarida etmoidotomiya qilingan. 20 nafar bemorning burun yon bo'shliqlarida qayta operatsiyalar o'tkazilgan: 22 nafar bemorda gaymorotomiya, 35 nafar bemorda etmoidotomiya amalga oshirilgan. 20 kishida qayta operatsiyalar o'tkazilgan, ammo shunga qaramasdan, ularda burun va burun yon bo'shliqlari polipozining qaytalanishi ro'y bergan. 164 nafar tekshiriluvchi shaxsdan 161 nafarining bo'shliqlarida turli jarrohlik aralashuvlari o'tkazilgan: ikki tomonlama gaymoroetmoidotomiya — 28 nafar, bir tomonlama gaymorotomiya va ikki tomonlama etmoidotomiya – 44 nafar, bir tomonlama gaymoroetmoidotomiya — 35 nafar, ikki tomonlama etmoidotomiya —48 nafar va bir tomonlama etmoidotomiya —6 nafar bemorda amalga oshirilgan. Uch nafar shaxsga jarrohlik aralashuviga umumiy moneliklari mavjudligi sababli o'tkazilmagan.

Tadqiqot natijalari: Davolash usuliga qarab bemorlarning uchta guruhi ajratildi. 1-guruhda (29 nafar kishi) operatsiyadan keyingi davrda faqat simptomatik davolash o'tkazilgan. 2-guruh bemorlariga (92 kishi) operatsiyadan keyin 12-15 kun davomida antigistamin preparatlari (dimedrol, pipolofen, suprastin, tavegil) va burun shilliq pardasiga 2-3 oy mobaynida kuniga 1 mahal oksikort yoki gioksizon malhamini surtish tayinlangan. 3-guruh bemorlariga (40 kishi) operatsiyadan keyingi davrda, yuqoridagi davodan tashqari, qo'shimcha ravishda har kuni tomir ichiga 30%li natriy tiosulfat eritmasi 5-10 ml dan 10 kun davomida yuborilgan. Tekshiriluvchilar ushbu preparatlarni yaxshi qabul qilishgan, hech qanday asorat kuzatilmagan.

Natriy tiosulfatni polipoz rinosinuit bilan kasallangan shaxslarda ilk marotaba qo'lladik, biz adabiyotlarda bunday xabarlarini topa olmadik.

Yuqori jag' bo'shliqlarida o'tkazilgan operativ aralashuvlar paytida polioplardan tashqari aksariyat bemorlarda (68%) yiringli eksudat ham topilgan, ushbu holat to'liq davolash uchun tegishli antibiotiklarni tayinlashni talab etdi.

Bizning kuzatishlarimiz zararlangan bo'shliqlar patologik tarkibdan maksimal darajada tozalangan bemorlarda nisbatan yaxshi natijalarga erishilganligini ko'rsatdi. Agar biror bir sababga ko'ra barcha bo'shliqlar polip va yiringdan tozalanmagan bo'lsa, polipozning erta qaytalanishi sodir bo'lgan. Tekshiriluvchilarning uchinchi guruhida yaqindagi va uzoq muddatli natijalar yaxshi

bo'lgan. Ularning uchtasida hid bilish funktsiyasi tiklangan, ushbu holat boshqa guruhlarda qayd etilmagan.

Uzoq muddatli natijalar (6 oydan 3 yilgacha) 60 nafar bemor - har bir guruhdagi 20 kishida o'rganildi. Birinchi guruhdagi 4 kishida a'lo darajadagi natijalar (burun orqali nafas olish erkin, poliplar yo'q) olingan, 6 kishida yaxshi natijalar (nafas olish erkin, burun gumbazida kichik poliplar mavjud), 10 kishida yomon natijalar (nafas olish qiyinlashgan, gumbaz va o'rta burun yo'lida poliplar mavjud) olingan.

Bemorlarning aksariyatida polipozning qaytalanishi operatsiyadan 6 oy o'tgach sodir bo'lgan.

Ikkinchi guruhdagi 7 kishida a'lo darajadagi, 11 kishida yaxshi, 2 kishida yomon natijalar kuzatilgan. Uchinchi guruhdagi 12 kishida a'lo darajadagi, 7 kishida yaxshi, 1 kishida yomon natijalar qayd etilgan.

Kuzatishlar uzoq muddatli remissiyaga erishish, poliplarning o'sishini sekinlashtirish va erta qaytalanishlar rivojlanishini oldini olish maqsadida jarrohlik aralashuvini dori-darmonlar terapiyasi bilan birlashtiriladigan kompleks davoni amalga oshirish lozimligini ko'rsatdi.

Xulosalar 1. Surunkali rinosinuitda polipozning qaytalanishini oldini olish uchun jarrohlik yo'li orqali davolashni natriy tiosulfat, kortikosteroidlar va antigistamin vositalardan foydalanishni o'z ichiga olgan dori-darmonlar bilan birlashtirish tavsiya etiladi. 2. Burun va burun yon bo'shliqlarining polipozi 68% hollarda yiringli zararlanish bilan kechganligi sababli, imkoni boricha, organizmning allergizatsiya o'chog'ini yo'qotish uchun yuqori jag' bo'shliqlari va g'alvirsimon suyakning sinuslarini, ba'zi hollarda esa boshqa bo'shliqlarni sanatsiya qilish hamda keyinchalik keng spektrli antibiotiklarni tayinlash lozim bo'ladi.

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